

ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Asenbaeva Klara Khudaybergenovna

Director of the State Preschool Educational
Organization No. 3 of the Department of Preschool
And School Education of the Nukus District
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15200934>

Annotation: The article is written about the violation of the laws of nature, the lack of environmental knowledge among people, environmental knowledge, the study of the structure, development and change of wildlife, the state of living beings on earth and ways to economically use natural resources

Key words: Ecological knowledge, laws of nature, air pollution, environmental education.

The most important ecological problems in our republic and measures for their prevention, the future of our planet, the fate of humanity today largely depend on the solution of ecological problems. The reason for the violation of the laws of nature is the lack of ecological knowledge among people, their inability to foresee the future state of nature. Ecological knowledge consists of studying the structure, development, and changes of living nature, the state of living beings on Earth, and mastering ways to use natural resources economically.

As a result of the destruction of the ozone layer and the drying up of the Aral Sea, environmental problems are arising. The release of toxic gases from factories and plants into the atmosphere, the release of toxic gases from cars into the atmosphere, and various explosions lead to the release of chlorine gases into the atmosphere, which leads to the destruction of the ozone layer. Air pollution and the increase in carbon dioxide in its composition pose a serious threat to human health. They were engaged in damming rivers, blocking their paths, creating artificial seas, and developing lands. These "achievements" disrupted the laws of nature and its complex and delicate balance. However, people did not think that these actions could lead to various disasters. As a result, grass pastures were destroyed, and new lands were developed.

Environmental education should be instilled in the younger generation from the family, from kindergarten age. The educational program of preschool educational institutions provides for fostering in children a love for Mother Nature, the ability to care for plants and animals, behavior in nature, cultivating interest in growing plants, caring for and protecting animals, not breaking trees, and not harassing animals, starting from the younger group. Environmental

education of children in preschool educational institutions is carried out in the following ways:

1. Visual (observation, viewing pictures, showing filmstrips).
2. Practical (in game form).
3. Oral (story, explanation, reading literary works).

Visual method. Observations are organized by the educator based on familiarizing children with plants, animals, weather, and adults' work in nature. Observations are conducted during lessons, walks, excursions, and in nature corners. Good results can be achieved if children combine it with practical activities. Diafilms used in preschool educational institutions were developed based on the preschool educational program. Diafilm helps the educator to interestingly convey the content of the program to the children based on a specific system. Through the television program "Who is it, what is it?" and the radio play "Journey to the World of Fairy Tales," children become acquainted with the nature of a particular region, the animal world, and the customs and traditions of its peoples.

Moral qualities are cultivated. Through the television programs shown in them, a comprehensive understanding of the processes occurring in nature, the world of plants and animals is formed. Practical method. When introducing children to nature, it is advisable to use didactic games with natural materials. Fruits, vegetables, tree branches, and houseplants can be used for this purpose. When introducing children to plants, the following games can be used: "Find the plants by name," "Find by leaves," "Find the described plant or fruit," etc. Oral method. In providing ecological education to children, the teacher's explanation, storytelling, use of folk proverbs and fables, and oral methods such as conversation play a significant role. For the upbringing of active defenders of nature, work is carried out with preschool children in the following areas:

1. Providing preschool children with concrete knowledge about the natural world and the interconnectedness of its phenomena.
2. Formation in children of activity related to nature, its preservation, and the increase of its wealth.

Oral method. In providing ecological education to children, the teacher's explanation, storytelling, use of folk proverbs and fables, and oral methods such as conversation play a significant role. For the upbringing of active defenders of nature, work is carried out with preschool children in the following areas:

1. Providing preschool children with concrete knowledge about the natural world and the interconnectedness of its phenomena.

2. Formation in children of activity related to nature, its preservation, and the increase of its wealth.

And the forest, the field?

And the river?

What is needed for plant growth?

How should children behave in the forest?

How did we take care of the birds?

Then you can talk about the conservation of wild animals, birds, and animals in other parts of the republic, and see pictures with children. The nature corner plays a significant role in fostering love for nature, a careful attitude towards it, care for plants and animals, and through this, fostering interest in nature, patriotism, diligence, and respect for the work of adults who preserve nature and increase its resources. Another important aspect of the nature corner is that children see it every day.

Under the teacher's guidance, the children systematically observe and care for the plants and animals in the nature corner. As a result, they acquire ideas and concepts about the diversity of the plant and animal world, their growth, development, and what conditions they need. The educator develops comparison skills in children. By comparing animals and plants with each other, they learn about the commonalities and differences between them, their characteristic features and properties. The teacher draws the children's attention to the beautiful flowering of plants, the shape and color of the leaves, the beautiful appearance and agile movements of the fish in the aquarium. As a result, children see these beauties with their eyes and feel them with their hearts, and their aesthetic taste grows.

As a result of observing and caring for plants and animals in the nature corner under the guidance of the teacher, a careful attitude towards nature is formed. It awakens in them the desire to contribute to the further flourishing of nature, as well as to participate in this process with the best possible work.

References:

1. Vygotsky L.S. Development of Higher Psychological Functions, Collected Works M. 1982.
2. Haytboev R., Amriddinova R.S. "Special Types of Tourism." Methodological instruction. Samarkand, 2008.